

D2.3 Privacy-preserving methods

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Control sheet

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable, we aim to provide Machine Learning practitioners with legal and technical context on data privacy protection. We summarise some key points of the GDPR, which is the most important legal framework in the European Union affecting data privacy, and we add some references with examples of documents with guidelines and good practices when it comes to data privacy in the context of Cooperative, Connected and Automated mobility.

We also explain and provide examples of some privacy preserving techniques, like anonymisation and pseudonymization and distributed learning. When explaining these two approaches we give examples of how we are applying them in the Althena project and how we plan to implement or explore those that we have yet to do so.

INTRODUCTION

Athena concept and approach

Athena is a project focused on research and innovation in the field of Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions that can give, under specific circumstances, better than human performance. Its goal is to develop CCAM technologies that are trustworthy, explainable, and accountable. We need to build the trust of society in general in AI so that it is an accepted technology that we will use or find in everyday life. We cannot trust that which we do not understand, so if we want the general public to accept the use of autonomous vehicles in our roads, we can't accept the models that will make decisions to be black boxes.

CCAM solutions are becoming more prevalent in vehicle technologies, leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) for perception, situational awareness, and decision-making components. However, AI can exhibit bias, unfairness, and extreme sensitivity to unexpected or non-standard inputs. Therefore, the next crucial step in technology development is to build AI that is explainable and trustworthy, incorporating important properties such as robustness, privacy, and explainability.

In an era where data is abundant and AI has immense potential to train autonomous vehicles, connected and cooperative automotive mobility solutions have surfaced. Every day, there's new hardware and software being developed and explored in this area, and how to make the models run faster, give better results or use resources in a more optimised way. Yet, AI's aspects of explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability responsibilities of AI outputs) remain largely unexplored.

The Athena project, funded by the EU, aims to lay the groundwork for trustworthy AI while maximizing its capabilities for societal benefit, making the AI we use more human centric.

Objectives

The project team will contribute to the development of explainable AI (XAI), conducting research on data, models, and testing. Additionally, they will make data and tools accessible through European data-sharing initiatives.

AITHENA will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual XiL set-ups with scalable MLOps). A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user identified group needs in CCAM applications. AITHENA will innovate proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI, and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions.

Demonstrators will show the AITHENA methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive, and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle-level).

Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

For Work package 2, in terms of data in general, the Althena project wants to create a representative set of data for the use cases of the project. After creating the dataset, the project also aims to create tools that will help developers to process, explore and select data to later train the models. There's also another important task that affects the other two, to explore privacy preserving methods along the whole data life cycle (creation, processing, training...). The quality of the models that will make decisions in our vehicles will be very dependent on the data that we are training the models with, so we want to have the best data that we can possibly find and the most amount of it. However, as ethical and as human centric as we think we are being by training the models with the best data quality and quantity possible, we can't forget about individual's right to privacy. We need to make sure that any identifiable data, regardless of if it's directly or indirectly identifiable, is protected, while also being available to use if the algorithm needs it.

GDPR

Introduction

The most important regulation in Europe regarding data privacy is The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1]. The GDPR establishes the level of control that people have over who can access their personal data. This law, not only applies to the EU but to any organization that deal with the data of a EU citizen, as it's a regulation on the data itself.

Definitions and key concepts

A very important feature of the GDPR is that it applies to personal data, which makes it the most important concept to define. On a legal level, what constitutes personal data is a binary, but, in reality, personal data is a spectrum [2].

In the context of GDPR, Art 4 (1) **personal data** is *“any **information** relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”*.

It's important to note that GDPR's text refers to 'information' rather than just data, indicating that the data appears to require some informational value for this regulation to apply. The difference is not always clear, and we will use the word data and assume that it contains information along this document, as future technology, or other data available to a person may turn data into information.

An individual is considered identifiable if they can be 'distinguished' from others with the data available. This does not require that the individual can be identified by a name, rather they could also be identified through alternative means such as a telephone number.

Some of the key concepts that are regulated by GDPR are:

- **User rights:** Users have the right to request access, correct, or delete the personal information that organisations collect about them. Users can also object to the processing of their data in certain circumstances.
- **Privacy by Design (PbD):** Organizations must proactively incorporate data protection measures into the design and operations of new systems and products. It should prevent any issues, as opposed to remedy the effects of them.
- **Consent:** Organizations must get explicit consent from users to process their data beyond necessary purposes, inaction or pre-ticked boxes do not comply with GDPR. The consent of the user must also be freely given, unambiguous and specific, meaning, the consent is given for well-defined and very specific circumstances and processing their data for anything outside what is described is illegal.
- **Data breach notifications:** If an organization suffers a data breach, they have 72 hours to notify their supervising authorities of the breach and must inform users as soon as possible.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** Organizations that process a significant amount of personal information need to appoint a DPO, who is responsible for ensuring GDPR compliance.

- **Transparency:** Organizations are required to have a privacy policy that clearly explains how they collect and use personal information.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA):** DPIAs are required if an organization's data processing activities could risk the rights and freedoms of individuals.

When can organizations use personal data

According to the GDPR, data can only be processed under one of these specific circumstances:

1. The subject of the data provides freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous consent to process the data.
2. Processing is necessary to execute or to prepare to enter a contract to which the data subject is a party.
3. You need to process it to comply with a legal obligation of yours.
4. You need to process the data to save somebody's life.
5. Processing is necessary to perform a task in the public interest or to carry out some official function.
6. You have a legitimate interest to process someone's personal data. This is the most flexible lawful basis, though the "fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject" always override your interests, especially if it's a child's data.

Personal data vs non-personal data

As GDPR only applies to personal data, it's very important to distinguish between what is personal data and what is non-personal data. We have mentioned the description the GDPR gives us for personal data, but it's still a pretty big challenge when it comes to real cases. There is data that is always non-personal (because it never related to an identified or identifiable natural person) and there is also data that once was personal but no longer is, as linkage to a natural person has been removed or in case the data was related to a legal or a deceased person.

Moreover, the principles of data protection should not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.

The graph in Figure 1 intends to help in identifying whether the data that we are dealing with is personal data or not. Under this criterion, it's important to know what would be considered a reasonable cost, time, or motivation; but this issue does not have an obvious answer. "Reasonable" is not an exact measure, but a subjective one. Although this kind of vagueness is makes it hard to interpret certain aspect of the GDPR, it's also done in purpose. When creating the GDPR, they didn't want it to quickly become obsolete, and they want it to be as general as possible. As mentioned before, if an entity processes large amount of data, they should appoint a DPO and if the entity doesn't have a DPO but has doubts about their case, they should consult with an expert.

Figure 1. Diagram to help identify personal data [2]

As there is this difficulty in discerning personal data, here are some examples of personal data.

- a name and surname
- a home address
- an email address such as name.surname@company.com
- an identification card number
- location data (for example the location data function on a mobile phone)*
- an Internet Protocol (IP) address
- a cookie ID*
- the advertising identifier of your phone
- other identifiers such as radio frequency identification (RFID) tags.
- data held by a hospital or doctor, which could be a symbol that uniquely identifies a person.

*Note that in some cases, there is a specific sectoral legislation regulating for instance the use of location data or the use of cookies – the ePrivacy Directive (Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002(OJ L 201, 31.7.2002, p. 37) and Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 (OJ L 364, 9.12.2004, p. 1)

Examples of data not considered personal data:

- a company registration number
- an email address such as info@company.com
- anonymised data.

Purpose of the data

The GDPR requires to consider how the data is being used to make decisions about specific individuals, in order to know if it's personal data. A piece of information that does not qualify as personal data for one organization could become personal data if a different organization came into possession of it based

on the impact this data could have on the individual. It all depends on the reason for which the organization is processing the data. If an organization processes data for the sole purpose of identifying someone, then the data is, by definition, personal data. To better understand this, let's see two examples of this:

- First, a photo of a street in the hands of a photographer is not personal data, while that same photo in the hands of an investigator who is working to identify the individuals and vehicles that were present on that street at that particular time would be considered personal data.
- Second, video surveillance or security footage whose sole purpose is to be used to identify individuals when and where authorities see fit should be considered as processing data about identifiable persons, even if, in some cases, the individuals recorded cannot be identified.

Applicability

GDPR applies to identifiable information, so a common solution is to anonymise the data. However, the anonymization process does fall under GDPR, as you are processing the raw data. Pseudonymised data also falls under GDPR, it can be traced back and, therefore, it's identifiable given the 2 sets of data we have: the anonymized data, and a set to revert the anonymization and trace it back. We will talk about anonymization and pseudonymization in Chapter 4.

It's also worth noting that as GDPR is centred around and protects data. It applies to personal data that belongs to a citizen of the EU, regardless of where the data is located or where the entity storing and processing the data is from.

Checklist

GDPR provides a checklist as a very interesting resource for entities to evaluate themselves and check if they comply with the rule. It acts as a guideline to know if we are taking into consideration the requirements of the law. The checklist can be found at:

<https://gdpr.eu/checklist/>

Rules in other countries

As of Q4 2023, the European Commission has so far recognised Andorra, Argentina, Canada (commercial organisations), Faroe Islands, Guernsey, Israel, Isle of Man, Japan, Jersey, New Zealand, Republic of Korea, Switzerland, the United Kingdom under the GDPR and the LED, the United States (commercial organisations participating in the EU-US Data Privacy Framework) and Uruguay as providing adequate protection [3].

Here is a list of countries with similar data privacy rules and links to their laws or references to them in English [4].

Europe

Switzerland ([Personal Data Protection Law](#))

The Middle East

Bahrain ([Personal Data Protection Law](#))

Israel ([Data Security Regulations](#))

Qatar ([Law No. 13](#))

Turkey ([Law on Protection of Personal Data No. 6698](#))

Africa

Kenya ([Data Protection Act](#))

Mauritius ([Data Protection Act](#))

Nigeria ([Data Protection Regulation](#))

South Africa ([Protection of Personal Information \(POPI\) Act](#))

Uganda ([Data Protection and Privacy Act, 2019](#))

Egypt ([Law No. 151](#)) [5]

Asia

Japan ([Act on the Protection of Personal Information](#))

South Korea ([Personal Information Protection Act](#)) [\[66\]](#)

India ([Personal Data Protection Bill PDPB](#))

Thailand ([Personal data protection Act](#))

Oceania

New Zealand ([Privacy Act](#))

South America

Argentina ([Personal Data Protection Act No 25,326](#))

Brazil ([General Data Protection Law LGPD](#))

Uruguay ([Act on the Protection of Personal Data and Habeas Data Action](#))

North America

Canada ([Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act \(PIPEDA\)](#))

OTHER LAWS AND GUIDELINES FOR PRIVACY PRESERVING IN CCAM

So far, we have exclusively talked about GDPR, which is a general rule about privacy. However, the Althena project looks at the Human-Centricity and ethics of AI specifically applied to a CCAM context. When looking at literature for data privacy in CCAM, we find that most resources cover data privacy in general. So in this chapter we cover some general standards about data privacy as well as different guidelines and standards specifically aimed at CCAM.

Standards relating to data privacy

ISO 2700 Series:

This series of standards cover a wide range of information security topics, including risk management, security controls, and security management systems. Some specific standards within the series include:

- **ISO/IEC 27001** provides requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an Information Security Management System.
- **ISO/IEC 27018** [6] provides guidelines for the protection of personal data in the cloud.
- **ISO/IEC 27040** [7] provides guidelines for protecting stored data, including data stored in the cloud.
- **ISO/IEC 27799** [8] provides guidelines for protecting personal health information (PHI).

ISO/IEC 23894 Guidance on risk management [9]

is a standard that provides guidance on risk management specifically related to artificial intelligence (AI). It is designed for organizations that develop, produce, deploy, or use products, systems, and services that utilize AI.

The guidance aims to assist organizations to integrate risk management into their AI-related activities and functions but also mentions privacy as part of their annex.

ISO/IEC 38507 Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations [10]

The objective of this document is to provide guidance for the governing body of an organization that is using, or is considering the use of, artificial intelligence (AI). They specifically address governance in the context of AI and have a section dedicated to the governance of data use.

IEEE P7002™ – Data Privacy Process [11]

The requirements for a systems/software engineering process for privacy-oriented considerations regarding products, services, and systems utilizing employee, customer, or other external user's personal data are defined by this standard. Organizations and projects that are developing and deploying products, systems, processes, and applications that involve personal information are candidate users of this standard.

ETSI GR SAI 002 Data Supply Chain Security [12]

This standard focuses on securing the data supply chain in Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems. It is specially focused on securing the integrity of the data that is used to train an AI system, but these procedures still help securing your data from data breaches. They provide standard cybersecurity practices as well as technologies like federated learning and cryptographic mechanisms such as hashing functions to ensure the integrity of the data.

ETSI GR SAI 005 Mitigation Strategy Report [13]

This standard is about securing Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems by mitigating known or potential threats. They identify the threats shown in Figure 2, where they categorise data extraction as part of the model inference process. They have a section called model enhancement mitigations against data extraction where they suggest two model enhancements for data privacy. They give a couple of examples that focus on protecting the data and the other one focusing on protecting the training process. They also suggest some model agnostic techniques that include adding noise to the confidence scores given by the model and limiting the queries made to the model.

Attack Types		Model Enhancement Mitigation Approaches	Model-agnostic Mitigation Approaches
Training	Poisoning attack	Clause 5.2.2	Clause 5.2.3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance data quality Data sanitization Block poisoning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output restoration
	Backdoor attack	Clause 5.3.2	Clause 5.3.3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance data quality Data sanitization Trigger detection Model restoration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trigger detection Trigger deactivation Backdoor detection
Inference	Evasion attack	Clause 6.2.2	Clause 6.2.3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data preprocessing Model hardening Robustness evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AE detection Input restoration Output restoration
	Model stealing	Clause 6.3.2	Clause 6.3.3
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IP management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limit the number of queries Stealing detection Output obfuscation Fingerprinting
	Data extraction	Clause 6.4.2	Clause 6.4.3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embed data privacy Training with privacy 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limit the number of queries Obfuscated confidence scores 	

Figure 2. Threats introduced by the use of AI

Specific regulations in CCAM

There are no specific regulations for privacy in CCAM exclusively, but we can find some documents that give guidelines or recommendations on how to apply GDPR or preserve the privacy of the data in a CCAM context.

A challenge that can arise from CAVs (Connected Autonomous Vehicles) in regard to collecting, processing and sharing personal data is the difficulty of obtaining consent from any and all individuals from which the vehicle may gather information from [14]. Different groups of actors may be involved: drivers, pedestrians, the drivers of vehicles surrounding the one gather data, passengers... And they may be identified with the information collected by the vehicle without their awareness, even though they

are affected. The collection of data in public spaces (like roads, cities...) may conflict with individual informed consent and realistic opt-out choices for the previously mentioned data subjects.

Guidelines 01/2020 on processing personal data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications [15]

These guidelines were adopted on March 9th 2021 and they serve as recommendations on how to apply GDPR. They also include a review and examples of how it has been applied so far, in some automotive applications.

As connected vehicles move into the mainstream, these vehicles are equipped with different sensors that collect and record data about vehicle conditions, driving style, mapping, the eye movement of the driver... Most of the data gathered by these connected vehicles can be considered personal data as it relates to either the drivers or passenger; whether they are directly linked to a name or not. With extra pieces of information, like their phone data, the vehicle's insurance or other documents... the data subject can become easily identifiable.

The scope of the document is the data processing to non-professional use of connected vehicles, company vehicles are out of the scope. Applications that a CAV may have that fall under these recommendations are: mobility management (route planning), vehicle management, road safety (warning of both internal and external events), entertainment (like smartphone connectivity or music), driver assistance and well-being (like fatigue detection).

One of the main risks they identify is location data, a point that needs special attention in CAVs. It may reveal not only personal data of an individual like their place of residence or work, but also sensitive data like their sexuality or religion depending on the locations they visit at certain times. They recommend paying attention to the frequency that the location is accessed depending on the functionality and giving specific information about why and how long this data is stored to users. They also recommend only activating location when needed, informing the user in some way of when the location is activated and an option to deactivate it at any time.

Another type of data that they recommend paying special attention to is biometric data. Following GDPR directive is enough, but the document reminds the reader that CAVs need to ensure that authentication with biometric data should be robust and resistant to attacks, that the biometric model for the authentication should only be stored in the vehicle and that the raw data used for the model should be immediately deleted after use.

In the document it also pointed out that with an increasing number of sensors in the vehicle we have a risk of collecting excessive amounts of data. In accordance with the GDPR, vehicles should only gather necessary data for the vehicle's functionalities.

In general, this document serves as a reminder of GDPR directives but a final point that is interesting is that vehicle passengers are not always properly informed about the gathering of the data, the focus is usually on the driver. Even with the driver's consent, they point out that an initial consent signed when starting to use the vehicle is not enough for further processing of the data in the future.

Ethics of Connected and Automated Vehicles: recommendations on road [14]

Each individual has the authority to determine a private sphere for personal conduct and self-development, including privacy of communications and the ability to control personal information sharing. Privacy is not only an ethical imperative but also an enforceable fundamental right in the EU.

Respect for privacy requires a valid legal basis for any collection, processing, use, or exchange of personal data.

The define 4 points to pay attention to, all of them in accordance with GDPR:

- Safeguard informational privacy and informed consent: they identify manufacturers and deployers of CAVs as what the GDPR defines as data controllers. They decide what data and with what purpose the data is recorded. They should facilitate data subjects' control over their data and the data subject's objection to collecting data that is not necessary for the proper operation of the vehicle must not result in denial of service.
- Enable user choice, seek informed consent options and develop related best practice industry standards. Policymakers, manufacturers and deployers and researchers should work together to give an alternative to "take it or leave it" models of consent, in accordance with Article 7 of the GDPR, which prohibits forced consent. Policymakers should also leverage competition and consumer law to counteract monopolies and enable user choice.
- Policy makers should develop measures to foster protection of individuals at group level (driver, pedestrian, passenger...). They should also develop guidelines for collection, assessment and sharing of non-personal data, third party personal data and anonymised data, as machine learning algorithms are able to infer personal data from those. As this is a new problem, they should do this work aided by researchers and with extensive public deliberation.
- Develop transparency strategies to inform road users about data collection and associated rights. Policymakers should work with manufacturers and deployers to develop meaningful, standardised transparency strategies to inform road users, including pedestrians, of data collection in a CAV operating area that may, directly or indirectly, cause risks to their privacy as they travel through such areas.

In the conclusions of this document, we can find a list of all the 20 recommendations and actions to take that they suggest as a summary.

ENISA Good Practices for the Security of Smart Cars [16]

This document is targeted to car manufacturers, Tier 1 and 2 component suppliers and aftermarket suppliers. They provide a threat taxonomy, in Figure 3, identifying risks at different levels.

Figure 3. ENISA's threat taxonomy

In the text, they also give some attack examples with countermeasures and what elements would be affected. We suggest looking at the original text for these examples as they provide very detailed

information. They finally describe good practices when it comes to security in smart cars that is summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. ENISA's good practices for security

ETSI TS 102 941 V1.4.1 (2021-01) Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Security; Trust and Privacy Management

A technical specification document that outlines the security, trust, and privacy management requirements for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS). The document provides a framework for the secure exchange of information between ITS stations, including vehicles, roadside units, and central systems. The goal of the specification is to ensure that ITS systems are secure, reliable, and able to protect the privacy of users. They argue that anonymity is insufficient for the protection of privacy in ITS and it is also unsuitable as ITS Stations should be observable in order to provide improved safety. Therefore, their recommendation is to employ pseudonymity and unlinkability techniques. Pseudonymity ensures that an ITS Stations may use a resource or service without disclosing its identity but can still be accountable for that use and unlinkability ensures that an ITS Stations may make multiple uses of resources or services without others being able to link them together.

ANONYMIZATION TECHNIQUES

Anonymization and pseudonymization definitions

It's important to differentiate between anonymization and pseudonymization, as we sometime believe that something like substitution of a name for an ID is anonymization, but if you keep track of what ID belongs to that name, that would be considered pseudonymization. Confusing pseudonymisation with anonymisation can create a false sense of security. In the diagrams below we can see a representation of the difference between those techniques, anonymization must be irreversible.

Figure 5. Pseudonymization diagram [17]

Figure 6. Anonymization diagram [17]

Although pseudonymisation has many uses, it should be distinguished from anonymisation, as it still allows identification using indirect means, which mean it only provides a limited protection for the identity of data subjects. Pseudonymization is a technique where a pseudonym is used, it is often possible to identify the data subject by analysing the underlying or related data.

Pseudonymisation is defined within the GDPR [1] as *“the processing of personal data in such a way that the data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, as long as such additional information is kept separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure non-attribution to an identified or identifiable individual”*. Unlike anonymisation, pseudonymisation techniques will not exempt controllers from the ambit of GDPR but it helps with meet data protection obligations.

Data can be considered “anonymised” from a data protection perspective when data subjects are no longer identifiable. If the data controller retains the raw data, or any key or other information which can be used to reverse the ‘anonymisation’ process and to identify a data subject, identification by the data controller must still be considered possible in most cases. Therefore, the data may not be considered

'anonymised', but merely 'pseudonymised' and thus remains personal data and should only be processed in accordance with Data Protection law.

Anonymisation is the process of removing personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that may lead to an individual being identified.

While there may be incentives for some organisations to process data in anonymised form, this technique may devalue the data, so that it is no longer of useful for some purposes. Therefore, before anonymization, consideration should be given to the purposes for which the data is to be used.

Pseudonymization is best used when:

- The data is being processed for a specific purpose, and some level of personal information is needed to achieve that purpose, but the information should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.
- There is a need to retain some personal information in order to monitor or enforce compliance with data protection laws, but the data should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.
- The data is being processed for scientific or statistical purposes, and personal information is needed for research purposes, but the data should not be directly linked to an individual's identity.

Anonymization, on the other hand, is best used when:

- The data is no longer needed for any specific purpose and the data controller has no intention of ever using it again.
- The data is being processed for scientific or statistical purposes, and it is not necessary to retain any personal information.
- The data is being shared with third parties and the data controller has no intention of using the data for any specific purpose.

Let's see some examples of pseudonymisation techniques [18]:

- **Encryption with secret key:** the holder of the key can easily decrypt the data. All personal data is contained in the dataset.
- **Hash function:** is a function which returns a fixed size output from an input of any size, and it can't be reversed. The risk is that hash functions are subject to brute force attacks.
- **Keyed-hash function with stored key:** this corresponds to a particular hash function which uses a secret key as an additional input.
- **Deterministic encryption or keyed-hash function with deletion of the key:** it's similar to selecting a random number as a pseudonym for each attribute in the database and then deleting the correspondence table.
- **Tokenization:** typically applied in the financial sector to replace card ID numbers by values that have reduced usefulness for an attacker.

And some anonymisation techniques:

- **Randomization**

- **Noise addition:** It involves altering attributes to make them less accurate while maintaining the overall distribution. Noise addition is a complementary measure, and it should not be assumed as a standalone solution.
- **Permutation:** This technique involves shuffling the values of attributes in a dataset, artificially linking some of them to different data subjects. However, it should be noted that if some attributes have a logical relationship or statistical correlation and are permuted independently, such a relationship will be destroyed.
- **Differential privacy:** It is an approach for providing privacy while sharing information about a group of individuals. The goal is to describe the patterns within the group while withholding information about specific individuals
- **Generalization**
 - **Aggregation and K-anonymity** aims to prevent a single data subject from being identifiable inside a group. Their attribute values are generalised so that each individual shares the same value. A way to do this, for example, is by using the average value of a certain attribute for all samples.
 - **L-diversity:** an extension to K-anonymity in which we make sure that every attribute has, at least, L different values.
 - **T-closeness** is a refinement of L-diversity where new classes are created that resemble the starting distribution.

Anonymization techniques used in the CCAM industry

Typical anonymization techniques in the CCAM industry are blurring and deep fake techniques. Blurring is usually understood to mean the use of Gaussian noise. This technique is used in Althena and is therefore described in more detail in "Methods to be explored in Althena."

Another technique used is deep fake technology. Deep fakes are synthetic media created using deep learning techniques to generate realistic-looking content, often altering the appearance or behaviour of people in videos and images. While deep fakes are primarily known for their potential abuse, e.g., for creating misleading content, they can also be used to preserve privacy, e.g., to anonymize faces and license plates.

For facial anonymization, so-called face swapping can be used, in which faces in the data are swapped with computer-generated faces or other selected faces. The algorithms maintain the consistency of facial features, expressions, and movements, ensuring the fake faces align with the original faces. This has the advantage that the images look completely normal at first glance after anonymization, as they do not contain any blurring. The assumption is that after using deep fake technologies, data is anonymized and also more usable for further processing steps. However, initial evaluations [19] show that either blurring or deep fake does not significantly change the predictive performance of a person detector, but studies in this area are still insufficient to make conclusive judgments.

A similar procedure is used for the anonymization of license plates, which is similar in principle to the face anonymization.

Methods to be explored in AITHENA

Detection and blurring

Althena is developing a tool for facial anonymization that includes automated blurring of faces on image data. The input of this tool is images in which people's faces are to be blurred. The output is the same images but with blurred faces.

The structure of the tool can be divided into three stages. In the first stage, people are recognized. This is used to pre-select image areas for subsequent face recognition in stage 2. Once the faces have been detected, they are blurred in stage 3.

The purpose of using a person recognizer in stage 1 is to increase the predictive performance of face recognition. Experiments have shown that this step leads to a reduction in false positives and an increase in true positives. The **faster RCNN** model [20] is used for person recognition, as it best compromises predictive performance and runtime. **SSD** [21] can be used as a substitute to shift this compromise towards runtime.

Stage 2 contains the bounding boxes of the person detector and performs face recognition. Two face recognizers are used to increase the recall: **MTCNN** [22] and **FaceBoxes** [23]. The predicted bounding boxes of both detectors are superimposed, which improves the recall, as both detectors result in different failure modes due to their different DNN architecture. A combination can compensate for the failure modes to a certain degree. One disadvantage of this approach is the increased runtime. To further improve predictive performance, the bounding boxes are resized by the person detector so that they have a minimum length in width or height of 128 px. The aspect ratios are preserved during this resizing. Experiments have shown that the person detector achieves a reduced predictive performance if the bounding boxes are too small.

Stage 3 blurs the bounding boxes from stage 2. A Gaussian blur with a 45x45 kernel is used for blurring. The content of the bounding box is then anonymized.

Hyperparameters for the person detector and the two face detectors were determined experimentally. These parameters can be changed accordingly to adjust precision and recall.

A fourth stage, which could include face segmentation (e.g., BiSeNet [24]), was omitted. This would have the advantage that people's faces could be blurred in an even more targeted manner. Still, it has been shown that the segmentation results suffer with faces with a very low resolution and thus worsen the anonymization result.

We can see an example of the output image of our method below in Figure 7, where 2 faces were detected and we applied the Gaussian blur.

Figure 7. Example of face blurring

Following the same idea, we built a License plate detector by using a YoloX [25] that was trained on private data. Following the same logic as with the faces, we detect the license plates, and we apply a median blur with a kernel size of 35 in this case. An example can be found in Figure 8, and in Figure 10 we have a diagram of the whole LP anonymization process including the blurring technique and the obfuscation technique that we will explain in the following section.

Figure 8. Example of LP blurring

Detection and Generative Substitution

There's a second approach that we are exploring in Althena where instead of blurring the object, it's obfuscated using a synthetically created object mimicking the real one. To better get an idea of this, we show an example in Figure 9 in which the license plates have been substituted by generic European ones. As this is a European project, the generative model has been trained to generate license plates that follow a European template for License plates, meaning, a blue stripe on the left side and an arrange of letters and numbers over white, as different countries have different designs.

Figure 9. LP synthetic obfuscation

In this case, instead of a bounding box we need a polygon, as we want to cover the license plate in whatever angle appears in the image with a synthetic one. If we decide to use synthetic obfuscation, in parallel to extracting the polygon that covers the license plate, we generate a fake license plate using a template and we apply a style transfer from the License plate detection so that it matches the original. For the style transfer, we use Fourier Domain Adaptation (FDA) for Semantic Segmentation [26]. The final step is to either blur the License plate detection area or obfuscate the original license plate with the synthetic one we created, depending on the anonymization method we chose to use. Below, we can see a diagram of the whole anonymization process.

Figure 10. License plate anonymization pipeline

Impact of anonymization techniques in the performance of AI models

As the data that we are anonymizing is used to train models that will be used in vehicles, we want these models to be as accurate as possible. This begs the question, is the model's performance negatively affected by the anonymization of the data? We have yet to conduct our own experiments where we want to see if any of the anonymization techniques affect the performance and if there is any difference between obfuscations and blurring. However, we have found some literature on this topic.

The authors of Zenseact Open Dataset [19] conducted the experiment by training two different object detectors with 3 different versions of the dataset: raw, blurred and with Deep Neural Anonymization (what we have called obfuscation in this document). They evaluate the performance of these models on the original validation set, with no anonymization. The two detectors they train are a Yolov7 and a Detectron2 pipeline that consists of a Faster-RCNN with a feature pyramid network and a ResNet-50 backbone. After evaluation, they report no significant impact of anonymization on their model. Results can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Result on detectors trained with Zenseact raw and anonymized.

<i>Pipeline</i>	<i>Mode</i>	<i>AP*</i>
<i>Faster-RCNN</i>	Original	30.23 ± 0.09
	DNAT	30.28 ± 0.03
	Blur	30.17 ± 0.06
<i>YOLOv7</i>	Original	33.62 ± 0.04
	DNAT	33.74 ± 0.09
	Blur	33.67 ± 0.01

*Average Precision (AP): the area under the PR (Precision Recall) Curve [27]

Another paper published this year [28] also analyses this impact. For their experiments they apply different anonymization methods: blurring, mask out and synthetic obfuscation, and they apply all three to face and full body. We show the results they report for instance segmentation with BDD100K dataset [29] in Table 2 and the results for key point extraction with COCO dataset [30] in Table 3.

Table 2. Results of instance segmentation for the class person by Hukkelås et al [28].

<i>Area</i>	<i>Mode</i>	<i>AP* (person)</i>
-	Raw	32.0 ± 0.0
<i>Face</i>	Blur	31.7 ± 0.1
	Mask-out	31.4 ± 0.1
	Obfuscation	31.6 ± 0.2
<i>Body</i>	Blur	0.5 ± 0.0
	Mask-out	0.0 ± 0.0
	Obfuscation	12.8 ± 0.1

Table 3. Results of key point detection by Hukkelås et al [14]

<i>Area</i>	<i>Mode</i>	<i>Box AP*</i>	<i>Keypoint AP*</i>
-	Raw	55.7 ± 0.0	65.2 ± 0.0
<i>Face</i>	Blur	50.3 ± 0.2	53.5 ± 0.2
	Mask-out	49.9 ± 0.2	52.0 ± 0.3
	Obfuscation	54.3 ± 0.1	60.6 ± 0.1
<i>Body</i>	Blur	17.8 ± 0.0	4.4 ± 0.1
	Mask-out	17.4 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1
	Obfuscation	24.0 ± 0.1	15.6 ± 0.1

Analysing the results, for BDD100K instance segmentation in Table 2, the difference in the Average Precision for the class person between the raw images and the anonymized ones is negligible when we anonymise only the face. Either of the options maintains pretty solid results, even in the case of mask out, so it seems like the detectors are able to learn appearance of a person as a class regardless of their face. However, as privacy concerns are an important topic, full body anonymization is preferable. Context clues, clothes etc can make a person identifiable even if their face is not shown in the image. For this case, obfuscation with a synthetically generated person would be preferable, so that the model

can learn the appearance of a person without risking their privacy. However, with the use of a synthetically generated person, the AP metric decreases by 63%.

In the task of key point extraction, which may be useful to analyse if a pedestrian is looking at the vehicle, and, therefore, aware of the vehicle approaching them, the anonymisation techniques have a bigger effect on the performance. We can see that for person detection (Box AP) with face anonymisation, the only anonymisation technique that gives similar result to the raw images is the obfuscation. It seems that in COCO dataset, the lack of a face in the images of people affects how well we can detect them. The authors theorise that the difference between these two datasets is that BDD100K's bounding boxes only take 1% of the image, which makes the impact smaller. For person detection with full body anonymisation on COCO dataset they get a 58% drop in performance, which is a bit smaller than that of the BDD100K dataset. As is logically expected, the performance of key point extraction is greatly impacted by anonymisation techniques. The impact, as expected, is lower when we look at face anonymization with a synthetic face compared to face blurring or mask out. Part of the key points in COCO dataset are in the face, as seen in Figure 11, so removing the face from the image of the person has a big impact in the task. As we can imagine, full body blurring and mask out makes key point extraction useless, and in the case of the synthetic person, the performance is reduced by a 75%.

Figure 11. Placement of COCO key points [30]

As of January 2024, we have not found any more literature on the impact of anonymisation, although we are planning to run some experiments ourselves and analyse it. The experiment we plan on running is the training of a person detection with 3 versions the same datasets: raw, face detection and blurring and person detection and blurring of the top part of the bounding box. We had the idea of running a person detection and blurring the top part when seeing the results of face detectors vs person detectors. As we want to automate the process of anonymisation as much as possible, we would like to explore the option of detecting people instead of faces as the results seem to be better in a few sequences we have tried so far, thanks to the difference is size and resolution of the images.

DISTRIBUTED TRAINING TECHNIQUES

Federated learning, also known as collaborative learning, is a sub-field of machine learning. It is set up so that multiple entities, often referred to as clients, collaboratively train a model while ensuring that their data remains decentralized. This stands in contrast to traditional machine learning settings where data is centrally stored.

Here's how it works:

- Federated learning aims at training a machine learning algorithm, for instance, deep neural networks, on multiple local datasets contained in local nodes without explicitly exchanging data samples.
- The general principle consists of training local models on local data samples and exchanging parameters (e.g., the weights and biases of a deep neural network) between these local nodes at some frequency to generate a global model shared by all nodes.
- The main difference between federated learning and distributed learning lies in the assumptions made on the properties of the local datasets. While distributed learning aims at parallelizing computing power, federated learning aims at training on heterogeneous datasets.

Traditional machine learning methods necessitate the centralization of training data on a single machine or data centre. The conventional process of constructing a deep learning solution involves several stages, such as data collection, training, regularization, and optimization, all of which require an implicit trust between the various parties involved. For example, when an organization shares a dataset with a team of data scientists, an implicit trust relationship is established between them. Any breach of this trust can impact the project's outcome. Deep learning algorithms undergo numerous regularization and optimization cycles, with researchers concentrating on adjusting the model's hyperparameters. It would be advantageous to decentralize the deep learning application lifecycle in such a way that organizations and data scientists could collaborate in a secure manner without the need for trust.

Federated Learning (FL) decentralizes the machine learning process to the edge. FL allows various authorities to collaboratively learn a shared predictive model while keeping all training data on their local devices, separating the capability to perform machine learning from the necessity to store data in the cloud. Compared to the centralized training approach, FL is a decentralized training method that allows vehicles to collaboratively learn a machine learning model while keeping all sensitive data, which may contain private information, on the vehicle itself.

Training in heterogeneous and potentially large networks presents new challenges that necessitate a significant shift from standard methods for large-scale machine learning, distributed optimization, and privacy-preserving data analysis.

Challenges of Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) presents a novel approach to machine learning by enabling data to remain on local devices, which is crucial for preserving user privacy. This method is increasingly being explored as a potential solution for empowering Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) to adapt to their environments without compromising privacy. The decentralized nature of FL, however, also generates new challenges, particularly in the realms of cybersecurity and privacy (which makes it contradictory

while it is also trying to prevent privacy concerns at the same time, by making the learning become decentralized) [31] [32].

One of the primary concerns in the implementation of FL is cybersecurity threats, including data poisoning and model poisoning, which can compromise the learning process and the safety of the vehicles. By introducing distributed learning, inherently multiple entry points for attacks are also introduced. In a centrally training strategy this is far less of an issue. These threats require robust defences to ensure the integrity of FL systems in applications like CAVs, where the stakes are exceptionally high due to the potential for real-world harm [33] [34]. Similarly, the preservation of privacy in CAVs-based FL is not limited to protecting user data but extends to safeguarding the learning models themselves against reverse-engineering and manipulation by malicious actors [34].

Furthermore, the complexity of designing FL systems necessitates careful consideration of privacy and security issues. The communication involved in FL, such as the sharing of model updates between vehicles, could potentially expose sensitive information. This highlights the need for strong encryption and anonymization techniques to secure the data and the learning process against unauthorized access and manipulation [33] [35].

Finally, the challenges of FL are also encompassing technical hurdles such as dealing with non-IID data, managing system heterogeneity, and ensuring efficient communication between the central server and participating devices. These challenges underline the importance of advanced optimization techniques, privacy-preserving methods, and the development of realistic benchmarks for evaluating and comparing FL methods [36] [37].

Despite these challenges, FL offers significant advantages, including collaborative model development, enhanced privacy and security, and improved performance over centralized systems. These benefits are particularly relevant in fields like healthcare and CCAM, where data privacy is paramount, and labelled data may be scarce or sensitive [36] [37] [38].

Concluding, while FL offers a promising avenue for the development of privacy-preserving, efficient, and adaptive learning systems in various domains, it also introduces a set of unique challenges that need to be addressed. Future research in this area should focus on developing robust defences against cybersecurity threats, designing secure and privacy-preserving learning systems, and establishing standards and regulations for the secure implementation of FL. A multidisciplinary approach, involving expertise in machine learning, cybersecurity, automotive engineering, and policymaking, will be crucial in overcoming these challenges and realizing the full potential of FL in applications such as CCAM. Exactly what AITHENA is aiming to focus on.

Distributed training in CCAM

For example, distributed training methods in CCAM applications can be used if data must not be exchanged across customers or national borders, i.e., the data remains local to the customer (clients). Distributed training methods (also known as federated learning [39]) aim to enable DNN training that ultimately achieves the same or at least similar predictive performance as centralized training, i.e., where all training data is available centrally. The distributed training methods used in practice relate to the exchange of weight updates or gradients after a certain number of training iterations. The simplest form provides an exchange after a single iteration so that the gradients are sent from the clients to the server and merged there. The merged gradients are then returned to the clients, and the weight update

is calculated and carried out. Variants of this perform this loop after several iterations, which requires less bandwidth and speeds up the entire training process. Another variant of this is weight averaging, in which the updated weights of the clients are transferred to the server rather than the gradients [40]. This can happen, for example, after a complete epoch has been run through or, in extreme cases, only after a complete training run has been carried out. Further variants arise when averaging the weights. Here, an equally weighted averaging or a weighted averaging can be carried out. Averaging on a layer basis or learning the weighting coefficients is even less common in practice [41].

Methods to be explored in AITHENA

For the AITHENA project we want to explore the possibility of using Federated learning as a way to avoid some of the issues of privacy. We will still need consent, secure storage of some of the data... However, we can use some of the data that we gather directly from the vehicle in the training of the models, and train them with raw data.

The framework we want to use is the NVIDIA FLARE framework [42]. NVIDIA FLARE (Federated Learning Application Runtime Environment) is an open-source, domain-agnostic, and extensible Software Development Kit (SDK) designed for Federated Learning. It empowers researchers and data scientists to adapt their existing Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) workflows to a federated paradigm. This allows platform developers to build secure, privacy-preserving offerings for distributed multi-party collaborations. By keeping all training data on local devices, FLARE decouples the ability to perform machine learning from the need to store data in the cloud.

Figure 12. Architecture of FL training with NVIDIA FLARE

We propose to have a central server, where all the processing done in the vehicles (acting as nodes) is gathered in a final AI network. For secure communication between the nodes and the central server, we would set up a VPN (Virtual Private Network). The way this works is iteratively following these steps:

1. The central server sends some initialization weights to the nodes. It can be the same weights for all the nodes or different.

2. The nodes train local models with the data they have locally available.
3. The nodes send the weight to the central server.
4. The central server trains a new model with the weights sent by all the nodes. There are different strategies to fuse all the weight together, which we will explore during the project.
5. The server sends updated weight to the nodes requiring them to evaluate the new weights with their data.
6. The nodes send their evaluation results to the central server.
7. The server selects the best weights and sends them to the nodes as new base weights for the network.

As a second option to this, we would like to explore the possibility of using Flower [43], an Open Source Federated Learning Framework. It offers high versatility as it is compatible with several frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, HuggingFace and pandas. It provides easy SSL-enabled connections, as well as different built-in aggregation options as well as giving the option to add a custom aggregation strategy. Regardless of the framework, the steps of the process described before are the same.

For the model monitoring, we propose to use MLFlow [44], an Open Source MLOps platform that allows us to keep track of trainings and evaluations, changes in the code or in the data. It also helps us visualise different metrics that we may be interested in. Finally, it provides model registry features, which means we can also save the weights and characteristics of the different models we train. For orchestrating all of these processes, we propose to use Apache Airflow [45], a tool based in Python, that allows us to schedule and monitor the whole workflow.

CONCLUSIONS

When it comes to machine learning and deep learning methods, data is the factor that will most affect the performance and the outcome of the models. But in our objective to find the biggest amount of data possible, we should never forget about protecting the privacy of the people represented in it. Legally, in the European Union, the most important directive that we need to follow is the GDPR. It is very important to identify clearly if we are dealing with any kind of personal data; where if we can identify directly or indirectly any information about an individual, we need to properly protect it. Although legally, data is either personal or not personal, in practice it is a more nuanced issue. If we are not completely sure if the data we are dealing with is personal, we should always ask an expert. We can find some literature on privacy in the context of CCAM, but although good practices exist, there are no legal issues that specifically affect this industry only. One of the biggest challenges in CCAM specific is getting the consent of all the data subjects as the vehicle records behaviour, images and such of not only people inside the vehicle, but also outside. In fact, even when looking only at the inside of the vehicle, consent can be a challenging issue. We need to take into consideration the driver and the passengers of a vehicle, something that needs extra attention in case of driving services like taxis, where the behaviour we record with the localisation is representative of the passenger, who will change every journey.

A very typical solution to dealing with personal data is to anonymise it but we need to make a clear difference between anonymization and pseudonymisation techniques and select the appropriate one. Anonymising our data can potentially take away some of its values, so we need to take this into account and select the most appropriate way to deal with the data. A solution that is being currently explored is Federated Learning, as we don't need to save the data and send it to a central server to train. We can directly use it to train in each vehicle and remove it after use. However, this technique has some challenges when it comes to cybersecurity and is subject to inverse engineering, so privacy is still an important issue to consider.

All in all, privacy is one of the biggest issues when dealing with large amounts of data as we usually do when using Artificial Intelligence. Companies and entities should always put into place security measures and use the appropriate privacy preserving techniques across their platforms.

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